

From steep-slope volcano to flat caldera floor

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Abstract:

Most laboratory experiments of caldera collapse have dealt with reservoir emptying below a flat-lying overburden without an overlying analogue volcanic edifice on top. The overload and the role of topography are then neglected so that the final flat floor within the caldera is directly linked to the initial one. In addition, caldera subsidence is commonly attributed to the collapse of the top of a magma chamber linked to eruptions delivering large amounts of volcanic products. Analogue experiments show that the deformation of a weak clay-rich core resulting from the hydrothermal alteration in a volcanic edifice can, in certain conditions, reproduce the structures of a caldera. In particular, it is a way to explain the flat floor of a caldera when resurfacing resulting from new eruptions or destructive processes seems unlikely.

Keywords: calderas, hydrothermal systems, modeling

32 **Caldera formation**

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34 Caldera formation is commonly associated with eruption of volcanic products and
35 attributed to the collapse of the roof of a reservoir resulting from magma withdrawal. This can
36 result either from a single eruption draining efficiently a huge volume of magma or from
37 recurrent eruptions and multiple dyking events leading to an incremental or step by step
38 collapse of the reservoir [e.g. Lipman, 1997, Munro and Rowland, 1996]. Whatever the
39 models, the collapsed surface corresponds approximately to the dimensions of the underlying
40 reservoir.

41 In some cases, geophysical data together with field data show that there is not a
42 reservoir large enough to permit such a collapse. For example, the classic caldera model is
43 unlikely for the Enclos Caldera at Piton de la Fournaise on Reunion Island [e.g. Rousset et al.,
44 1989; Nercessian et al., 1996; Briole et al., 1998; Malengreau et al., 1999] or on the French
45 Polynesia Island of Nuku Hiva [Legendre et al, 2005; Maury et al., 2005].

46 Hot fluid circulation of both groundwater and magmatic gas deeply alters volcanic
47 rock and produce volume loss together with clay-rich zones able to flow under their own
48 weight. Recent studies have shown that such altered rocks form large zones within edifices
49 and initiate sector collapses [Lopez and Williams, 1993; Day, 1996; Vallance and Scott, 1997;
50 Voight and Elsworth, 1997; van Wyk de Vries et al., 2000; Reid et al., 2001; Cecchi et al.,
51 2005]. Also, the core of the volcano may become unstable if conditions of weak lateral
52 confinement exist at the boundary of the hydrothermal system, which then flows laterally.
53 The ensuing collapse of the central part of the edifice may then create a caldera-like structure
54 apparently similar to classical calderas but named "caldera-like" as the drained material is not
55 magma but altered rock [Merle and Lénat, 2003 ; Merle et al., 2006].

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58 **Caldera floor topography**

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60 The classic image of a caldera structure is that of a huge cauldron with a flat floor
61 surrounded by a ring fault exhibiting a circular vertical cliff of several hundred meters high.
62 The question is rarely asked as to how and by which mechanism such a flat floor can form
63 starting from a steep-slope cone. Many young caldera structures are filled by thick volcanic
64 sequences and rare are those that are eroded to the original surface. Very little evidence is thus
65 available to evaluate the degree of disruption of the floor and the initial intra-caldera slopes.

66 Concerning previous experimental studies on caldera formation, only recent studies
67 took the initial topography of a volcanic cone into account. Using a cone with a slope of 10°
68 and a flattened apex, Troll et al. [2002] describe both piecemeal subsidence as a consequence
69 of inflation and deflation of the chamber and piston subsidence linked to simple chamber
70 emptying, but the final topography is not described. Walter and Troll [2001] outline, in
71 experiments of chamber deflation under a cone, an initial apical sagging and a tilt of the
72 flanks until a delayed bench-like collapse of the caldera floor. Lavallée et al. [2004] points out
73 the problem of initial topography in scaled physical models and illustrates the real influence
74 of pre-existing relief upon the style of caldera subsidence due to magma withdrawal.

75 In this paper, we investigate experimentally the formation of caldera-like structures
76 resulting from the ductile flow of very large hydrothermal systems. As opposed to previous
77 experiments on that matter [Merle and Lénat, 2003; Merle et al., 2006], no reduction of lateral
78 stresses to trigger or speed up the collapse process is introduced in the experimental
79 procedure. We pay special attention to the slope modification of the initial cone during the
80 deformation.

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83 **Experimental procedure**

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85 In many previous experiments on caldera formation, the reservoir was simulated using
86 a balloon or a bladder filled with air or water and buried within a cohesive material [Kennedy
87 et al., 2004, Lavallée et al., 2004, Holohan et al., 2005]. Sometimes, viscous materials like
88 golden syrup, silicone or dry ice are directly emplaced into the cohesive material [Komuro,
89 1987; Acocella et al., 2000; Roche et al., 2000]. In some experiments, inflation of the balloon
90 predates deflation to simulate a complete process from magma arrival to magma emptying. In
91 experiments conducted here, the goal is to investigate the effect of a low-strength zone
92 simulating the hydrothermal system localised in the core of a cohesive edifice and no inflation
93 process has to be simulated.

94 The experimental setup consists of a piece of silicone upon which a steep-slope cone
95 of cohesive material is built. A layering of different colours helps to highlight the structures
96 after deformation. The diameter of the cone is in the range from 5 to 30 cm (i.e. 5 to 30 km in
97 nature) and its slope is about 30 degrees. The internal structure is observed via cross-sections
98 cut through the models after deformation. The topography of the analogue model is preserved
99 by pouring new sand on top of the model, which is then wet with water, to make possible to
100 cut cross-sections in the solidified model.

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103 **Scaling**

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105 The clay-rich altered core is considered to behave as a viscous fluid and is simulated
106 by silicone putty emplaced in the central part of the analogue model [e.g. van Wyk de Vries et

107 al., 2000]. The brittle part of the edifice is simulated by a dry sand/plaster mixture as in most
108 analogue experiments on volcano deformation [e.g. Donnadieu and Merle, 1998].

109 The shape of hydrothermal systems is poorly known as their boundaries have no sharp
110 limits and are difficult to image accurately via geophysical approaches. When studying the
111 geo-electrical model of the central part of Piton de la Fournaise volcano, Lénat et al. [2000]
112 detected the upper limit of a zone of low conductivity (0-20 ohm.m) in the Enclos caldera
113 inferred to be the hydrothermal system. The overall shape of the zone mimics a low-slope
114 cone. From this information and to simplify the experimental procedure, we choose to test
115 both conical and cylindrical shape ductile structures in our experiments.

116 Similarity conditions are achieved through a set of Π dimensionless numbers [see
117 Merle and Borgia, 1996], which must be of the same order of magnitude in nature and
118 experiments [Table 1, 2]. The Reynolds number is the only one to be different in nature and
119 experiments. However, the very small values of Π_6 (10^{-17} in nature and 10^{-10} in experiments)
120 show that the inertial forces are negligible with respect to the viscous forces both in nature
121 and experiments. Thus, this number need receive no further consideration.

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124 **Results**

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126 A control experiment has first been carried out where a piece of silicone was buried
127 into a pile of horizontal sand layers. Such a configuration is perfectly stable and no
128 deformation can be observed.

129 A set of experiments with a 30°-slope cone has then been conducted varying the shape
130 and thickness of the silicone. These experiments do not reveal notable differences in the
131 whole deformation process, even when using a slightly conical or a cylindrical piece of

132 silicone, so that all following experiments have been done with a low to medium height-to-
133 diameter ratio cylinder (Fig. 1). Subsequently, cone slope variation has been tested.

134 The most informative experiments are those built with steep-slope cones ($>25^\circ$).
135 Deformation starts instantaneously and reveals three successive stages. The first one
136 corresponds to rapid flattening on top of the cone without lateral bulging. This deflation stage
137 delimits a large upper flat area. This is the major change of the shape of the analogue volcano
138 observed during the whole duration of the experiment. The second stage corresponds to the
139 progressive appearance of a circular ring fault surrounding the flat zone formed previously.
140 The third and last stage is associated with the collapse of the flat zone along the ring fault,
141 leading to a caldera-like structure. Its topography contrasts remarkably with the undisturbed
142 external slopes of the cone (Fig. 2). A slight steepening of these external slopes is sometimes
143 observed next to the ring fault during the caldera-like formation and may generate local sector
144 collapses.

145 Cross-sections reveal that the brittle cone has flattened without any internal faults or
146 fractures. The shape of the silicone has evolved with time and the initially horizontal or
147 convex upper limit has become concave downward, centered below the former summit of the
148 cone. The ring fault outlines the circular edge of the silicone, which has intruded upward
149 within the fracture, up to the surface in some experiments (Fig. 2).

150 Other experiments have been conducted diminishing the slope of the overlying cone.
151 The deformation starts more slowly than in steep-slope experiments and may not reach the
152 formation of a caldera-like structure. With slopes less than 15 degrees, a slight depression
153 forms on top of the analogue volcano and no ring fault can be detected. When slopes are
154 nearly flat, no deformation occurs. This indicates that the slope of the cone has a major
155 influence on the deformation process.

156 Decreasing the thickness of the silicone leads to a smaller offset along the ring fault as
157 less ductile material can flow underneath. The deformational process can even be inhibited
158 when there is not enough silicone to allow ductile flow.

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161 **Interpretation**

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163 Given the lack of deformation for a flat topography, it appears that the formation of a
164 caldera-like structure is due to the presence of a cone above a ductile body and is dependant
165 upon the boundary conditions along the edge of this body. The distribution of the load (ρgh)
166 above the silicone is not uniform and a radial and horizontal overburden gradient, ($d\rho gh/dx$,
167 Fig. 3), is evidenced from high loading at the centre of the silicone, that is under the summit
168 of the cone, to low loading along the edges. This radial gradient promotes the deformation of
169 the silicone that narrows in the centre due to the weight of the summit of the cone and flows
170 laterally to the low overloaded edges. This ductile deformation is accompanied by the
171 subsidence of the upper part of the cone, which forms the upper flat area. It is noteworthy that
172 the flat floor is formed before the onset of the caldera-like collapse.

173 Further deformation is dependant on the intensity of the overburden gradient. With
174 low slopes (i.e. low overburden gradient), the deformation may stop and the evolution to the
175 formation of a caldera-like structure does not occur. With steep slopes (i.e. high gradient), the
176 silicone that is blocked laterally by the analogue volcano flank may overcome the vertical
177 overburden, which is relatively low there, and start to rise up. At the surface, this stage is
178 associated with the initiation of the ring fault that foreshadows the collapse. However, offset
179 remains limited at this stage as, very much like classic calderas, a real collapse of the roof
180 requires enough drainage of the ductile material. For this to occur, the hydrothermal zone

181 must be large enough and as close to the surface as possible, which permits the overburden
182 resistance to be overcome. Then, the altered rock of the hydrothermal system would be
183 squeezed upward along the edges, enlarging the ring fault, which is unrecognisable at depth
184 (cross-section in fig. 2) and causing the slight slope increase next to the ring fault. In most
185 experiments, the silicone pierces the surface along the ring-fault, and flows slowly downward
186 (Fig. 2). Such emptying of the ductile body is very efficient and speeds up the caldera-like
187 collapse.

188 In experiments, the silicone flows as a viscous material when reaching the surface.
189 This is a limitation of the analogue modelling, which cannot reproduce the rheology changes
190 probably sustained by the hydrothermally altered rock during its rise and cooling along the
191 ring fault. In nature, rather than a viscous flow, it would appear at the surface as a mix of
192 breccias and clay in variable proportions.

193 Locating the ductile body below a certain depth, that is below the base of the volcano,
194 inhibits the process as the cone effect becomes too low to trigger deformation. To a very good
195 approximation, a ductile body deeply buried under the base of the volcano makes the
196 experimental conditions identical to that of the control experiment.

197 In a complementary experiment, the effect of a fault lowering part of a volcano has
198 been tested, according to the process proposed by Merle et al. [2006]. They studied the
199 formation of the caldera-like structure on Nuku Hiva Island, supposed to result from weak
200 lateral confinement of the hydrothermal system. The authors used simplified models, with
201 flat-lying topography, to demonstrate the consistency of the model. When using a low-slope
202 cone instead of a flat topography, the three successive stages described above can again be
203 observed. Firstly, the summit of the cone flattens at the onset of the deformation to form a
204 large upper flat area. Secondly, slow subsurface lateral spreading of the silicone initiates a
205 ring fault. Thirdly, collapse occurs along the ring fault to form a caldera-like structure

206 breached on one side (Fig. 4). This suggests that the general process described here may
207 happen in different tectonic environments and takes place once the ductile body inside the
208 volcano can easily be deformed.

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211 **Conclusions**

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213 In the situation of caldera-like formation by ductile deformation of the hydrothermal
214 system, experiments show that the flat floor forms early by summit flattening before the
215 formation of the ring fault along which the collapse occurs. This happens only when the
216 hydrothermal system of the volcano can deform within the volcano to modify the natural
217 equilibrium between ductile altered rock and brittle overburden on the edges of the system.
218 Experiments shown here are scaled for the deformation of a clay-rich core and do not apply to
219 the formation of a classic caldera by emptying of a magmatic reservoir. However, it cannot be
220 ruled out that the process of flat floor caldera-like formation is similar to that of a classic
221 caldera, given that the rheology of the whole system is very close, composed of a viscous
222 reservoir able to flow surmounted by a pile of brittle volcanic rocks.

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228 **References Cited:**

229

230 Acocella, V., F. Cifelli, and R. Funicello (2000), Analogue models of collapse calderas and
231 resurgent domes, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 104, 81-96.

232 Briole, P., P. Bachèlery, B. McGuire, J. Moss, J. C. Ruegg, and P. Sabourault (1998),
233 Deformation of Piton de la Fournaise: Evolution of the monitoring techniques and
234 knowledge acquired in the last five years, in *Proceedings, 2nd Workshop on European
235 Laboratory Volcanoes, Santorini, Greece, 1996*, edited by R. Casale et al., *European
236 Commission, Brussels*, pp.467–474.

237 Cecchi, E., B. van Wyk de Vries, and J-M. Lavest (2005), Flank spreading and collapse of
238 weak-cored volcanoes, *Bull. Volcanol.*, 67, 72-91.

239 Day, S. J. (1996), Hydrothermal pore fluid pressure and the stability of porous, permeable
240 volcano, *Volcano Instability on the Earth and Other Planets*, edited by W. J. McGuire,
241 A. P. Jones, and J. Neuberg, *Geological Society (London) Special Publication 110*, p.77-
242 93.

243 Donnadieu, F. and O. Merle (1998), Experiments on the indentation process during
244 cryptodome intrusion : new insights into Mt St Helens deformation, *Geology*, 26, 79-82.

245 Holohan, E. P., V. R. Troll, T. R. Walter, S. Münn, S. McDonnell, and Z. K. Shipton (2005),
246 Elliptical calderas in active tectonic settings: an experimental approach, *J. Volcanol.
247 Geotherm. Res.*, 144, 119-136.

248 Kennedy, B., J. Stix, J.W. Vallance, Y. Lavallée, and M.-A. Longpré (2004), Controls on
249 caldera structure: results from analogue sandbox modeling, *Geol. Soc. of Am. Bull.*, 116,
250 515-524.

251 Komuro, H. (1987), Experiments on cauldron formation: a polygonal cauldron and ring
252 fractures, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 31, 139-149.

253 Lavallée, Y., J. Stix, B. Kennedy, M. Richer, and M.-A. Longpré (2004), Caldera subsidence
254 in areas of variable topographic relief: results from analogue modeling, *J. Volcanol.*
255 *Geotherm. Res.*, 129, 219-236.

256 Legendre, C., R.C. Maury, D. Savanier, J. Cotten, C. Chauvel, C. Hémond, C. Bollinger, G.
257 Guille, S. Blais, and P. Rossi (2005), The origin of intermediate and evolved lavas in the
258 Marquesas archipelago: an example from Nuku Hiva island (Marquesas, French
259 Polynesia), *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 143, 293-317.

260 Lenat, J.-F., D. Fitterman, D. B. Jackson, and P. Labazuy (2000), Geoelectrical structure of
261 the central zone of Piton de la Fournaise volcano (Réunion), *Bull. Volcanol.*, 62, 75-89.

262 Lipman, P. W. (1997), Subsidence of ash-flow calderas: relation to caldera size and magma
263 chamber geometry, *Bull. Volcanol.*, 59, 198-218.

264 López, D. L., and S. N. Williams (1993), Catastrophic volcanic collapse: relation to
265 hydrothermal processes, *Science*, 260, 1794-1796.

266 Malengreau, B., J.-F. Lénat, and J.-L. Froger (1999), Structure of Réunion Island (Indian
267 Ocean) inferred from the interpretation of gravity anomalies, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm.*
268 *Res.*, 88, 131-146.

269 Maury, R. C., G. Guille, C. Legendre, D. Savanier, H. Guillou, P. Rossi, et S. Blais (2005),
270 Notice explicative, carte géologique de la France (1/50000), feuille de Nuku Hiva,
271 Polynésie française : Orléans, BRGM, Archipel des Marquises : Service Géologique
272 National, Editions du BRGM.

273 Merle, O. and A. Borgia (1996), Scaled experiments on volcanic spreading, *J. Geophys. Res.*,
274 101(B6), 13805-13817.

275 Merle, O., and J.-F. Lénat (2003), Hybrid collapse mechanism at Piton de la Fournaise
276 volcano, Reunion Island, Indian Ocean, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 108(B3), 2166.

- 277 Merle, O., S. Barde Cabusson, R. C. Maury, C. Legendre, G. Guille, and S. Blais (2006),
278 Caldera core collapse triggered by regional faulting, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 158,
279 269-280.
- 280 Munro, D. C., and S. K. Rowland (1996), Caldera morphology in the western Galápagos and
281 implications for volcano eruptive behavior and mechanisms of caldera formation, *J.*
282 *Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 72, 85-100.
- 283 Nercessian, A., A. Hirn, J.-C. Lepine, and M. Sapin (1996), Internal structure of Piton de la
284 Fournaise Volcano from seismic wave propagation and earthquake distribution, *J.*
285 *Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 70, 123-143.
- 286 Reid, M. E., T. W. Sisson, and D.L. Brien (2001), Volcano collapse promoted by
287 hydrothermal alteration and edifice shape, Mount Rainier, Washington, *Geology*, 29(9),
288 779-782.
- 289 Roche, O., T. H. Druitt, and O. Merle (2000), Experimental study of caldera formation, *J.*
290 *Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 105(B1), 395-416.
- 291 Rousset, D., A. Lesquer, A. Bonneville, and J.-F. Lénat (1989), Complete gravity study of
292 Piton de la Fournaise volcano, Reunion, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 36, 37-52.
- 293 Troll, V. R., T. R. Walter, and H.-U. Schmincke (2002), Cyclic caldera collapse: piston or
294 piecemeal subsidence? Field and experimental evidence, *Geology*, 30(2), 135-138.
- 295 Vallance, J. W., and K. M. Scott (1997), The Osceola Mudflow from Mont Rainier:
296 Sedimentology and hazard implications of a huge clay-rich debris flow, *Geol. Soc. Am.*
297 *Bull.*, 109(2), 143-163.
- 298 van Wyk de Vries, B., N. Kerle, and D. Petley (2000), Sector collapse forming at Casita
299 volcano, Nicaragua, *Geology*, 28(2), 167-170.
- 300 Voight B., D. Elsworth (1997), Failure of volcano slope, *Géotechnique*, 47(1), 1-31.

301 Walter, T. R., V. R. Troll (2001), Formation of caldera periphery faults: an experimental
302 study, *Bull. Volcanol.*, 63, 191-203.

303

304 **Figure captions**

305

306 **Fig. 1:** Sketch of the model: a ductile core of silicone is embedded into a brittle cone.

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308 **Fig. 2:** Caldera-like formation: summit flattening (Fig. 2.2) occurs early and is followed by
309 the formation of the ring fault (Fig. 2.3) along which collapse takes place (Fig. 2.4).

310 Photographs of both panoramic and cross-section views reveal a flat caldera-like floor
311 surrounded by steep slopes.

312

313 **Fig. 3:** Load distribution above the weak zone. In steep slope ($>25^\circ$) experiments, the high
314 overburden gradient in the x direction allows the upward ductile flow along the edge to
315 overcome the strength of the overlying brittle material, which does not occur with gentle
316 slopes ($<15^\circ$) experiments.

317

318 **Fig. 4:** Complementary gentle slopes ($< 15^\circ$) experiment. Weak lateral confinement is
319 achieved from normal faulting lowering part of the edifice. The same three successive
320 stages of deflation, faulting and collapse as shown on figure 2 are observed with time.

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TABLE 1. PARAMETERS

Variable	Definition	Nature	Model
B	Diameter of the cone	5-30 km	5-30 cm
D	Diameter of the ductile core	1-15 km	1-15 cm
H	Offset along the normal fault	1-2 km	1-2 cm
h	Height of the brittle cone	1-3 km	1-3 cm
ϕ	Angle of friction		33°-37°
g	Gravitational acceleration		9.81
ρ_v	Density of the brittle cone	2500 kg m ⁻³	1300 kg m ⁻³
ρ_h	Density of the ductile core	1600 kg m ⁻³	1000 kg m ⁻³
τ_0	Cohesion	10 ⁷ Pa	50 Pa
t	Time span for caldera formation	300 y	1 h
η	Viscosity of the ductile core	10 ¹⁶ Pa.s	5 × 10 ⁴ Pa.s

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TABLE 2. THE 7 DIMENSIONLESS NUMBERS

	Definition	Calculation	Nature	Model
	Geometric ratios	$\Pi_1 = \frac{B}{D}$		5 - 2
	↔ scale 1 km = 1 cm	$\Pi_2 = \frac{H}{D}$		1 - 1.3
Brittle material	Angle of friction	$\Pi_3 = \phi$		33° - 37°
	Gravitational stress/cohesion	$\Pi_4 = \frac{\rho_v g h}{\tau_0}$	2.5 - 7.3	2.6 - 7.7
Ductile material	Gravitational force/viscous force	$\Pi_5 = \frac{\rho_h g h t}{\eta}$	14.8 - 44.5	7 - 21.2
	Reynolds number	$\Pi_6 = \frac{\rho_h h^2}{\eta t}$	1.7x10 ⁻¹⁷ - 1.5x10 ⁻¹⁶	5.6x10 ⁻¹⁰ - 5x10 ⁻⁹
	Density ratio	$\Pi_7 = \frac{\rho_v}{\rho_h}$	1.5	1.3

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